

Investigating Buckling Of Functionally Graded Sandwich Nano-Beams with Higher Order Shear Deformation Theory

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Abstract

The present research focuses on the analysis of buckling in FGM beams, incorporating a non-local theory and Poisson's effect within its analytical framework. A higher-order transverse shear field has been employed, utilizing a novel warping shape function. The equilibrium equations have been derived analytically from energy principles, with the numerical solution of these equations based on energy minimisation using the Ritz method. A comparative study was conducted to explore the variation of the dimensionless critical buckling with respect to different higher-order deformation theories. This study utilised a simply supported FGM (metal-ceramic) beam, excluding Poisson's effect, to analyse the influence of various parameters. A secondary application was performed on a sandwich beam, incorporating nonlocal theory and Poisson's effect, to investigate the effects of different beam slenderness ratios and variations in volume fraction index. The results of the dimensionless critical buckling analysis demonstrated that the Poisson effect significantly influenced the behaviour of the system. Furthermore, it was observed that the nonlocal effect behaves in a distinct manner depending on the beam slenderness, a phenomenon attributable to its interconnection with shear effects, which are more pronounced in short beams.

Keywords: Buckling analysis; FGM; Beam theory; Nonlocal theory; Poisson's effect; Rayleigh-Ritz method

1. Introduction

Functionally Graded Materials (FGMs) have emerged as a novel solution to address the mechanical and thermal challenges faced by contemporary structures through the integration of heterogeneous material properties. These materials are distinguished by their continuous and controlled variation in composition and properties, facilitating a seamless transition between constituent materials [1]. This unique material configuration offers significant advantages in mitigating degradation induced by temperature gradients and enhancing thermal shock resistance [2]. Consequently, FGMs have garnered considerable attention in aerospace applications, where components must withstand elevated temperatures and stresses while minimizing the occurrence of cracking and delamination[3], [4].

The buckling behaviour of FGM structures has become a dynamic area of research due to the critical role of FGMs in structural applications. Extensive examination of the buckling phenomenon in FGM beams and plates has been conducted using both analytical and numerical approaches to evaluate the influence of material gradients on buckling loads [5], [6], [7]. Notably, the Ritz method has been employed to analyse thermal effects on the buckling response of laminated and FGM beams[8], [9].

Shear deformation theories play a fundamental role in the analysis of FGM structures subjected to buckling, as they facilitate the incorporation of more realistic effects compared to Euler-Bernoulli beam theories[10]. The Timoshenko beam theory, for instance, accounts for shear deformation and rotations, which is essential for composite materials with variable stiffness such as FGMs [11], [12]. Comprehensive reviews of shear deformation approaches applied to FGMs have demonstrated that higher-order models, particularly those based on hyperbolic functions, provide more accurate estimations of shear deformations, especially under combined thermal and mechanical loading conditions[13], [14].

The Poisson effect, which correlates axial and transverse deformation, constitutes an essential consideration in analysing the behaviour of FGM structures under buckling loads. This effect assumes particular significance in heterogeneous structures, as it directly influences stress distribution and deformation modes [15]. Research has demonstrated that the omission of the Poisson effect may lead to erroneous evaluations of critical buckling loads, particularly in laminated beams and composite structures [16], [17].

The application of nonlocal elasticity in the buckling analysis of FGM structures has become crucial for small-scale structures [18]. The nonlocal elasticity theory, developed by Eringen [19], incorporates short-range interactions between material particles [20], [21], [22], which is particularly relevant for nanoscale FGM structures. Studies have investigated the buckling of Timoshenko beams with nonlocal effects, demonstrating that the introduction of nonlocal parameters enables more accurate predictions of buckling behaviour [23], [24], [25].

In conclusion, the study of buckling behaviour in FGM structures encompasses a wide range of theoretical and analytical approaches, including shear deformation theories, nonlocal elasticity, and the consideration of elastic foundations. These advanced methodologies contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the complex

mechanical behaviour of FGMs, paving the way for their optimal utilization in various engineering applications.

2. Objectives

The objective of this article is to study the influence of the Poisson effect and nonlocal theory on the critical buckling of FGM nano-beams. A higher-order shear deformation theory with a novel shape function is developed without the use of a shear correction factor. Numerical solutions of the equilibrium equations are presented for a simply supported beam using the Rayleigh-Ritz method

3. Mathematical Formulation

In the study we considered a supported-supported FGM sandwich beam of length L and rectangular cross-section $b \times h$. The beam is composed of 3 layers as shown in the **Fig 1**. The material properties for each layer, like Young's modulus E , can be expressed as:

$$E(z) = (E_c - E_m) \cdot V_c + E_m \quad (1)$$

With :

$$\begin{cases} V_c^1(z) = \left(\frac{z-h_0}{h_1-h_0}\right)^p & \text{for } z \in [h_0, h_1] \\ V_c^2(z) = 1 & \text{for } z \in [h_1, h_2] \\ V_c^3(z) = \left(\frac{z-h_0}{h_2-h_3}\right)^p & \text{for } z \in [h_2, h_3] \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where p is the power-law index; the subscripts m and c denote the metallic and ceramic constituents respectively, and V_c represents the volume fraction of the ceramic phase in the beam

The chosen coordinate system (x, y, z) is centered at the middle of the plate, with the coordinate parameters defined such that: $0 \leq x \leq L$, $0 \leq y \leq b$ and $-h/2 \leq z \leq h/2$.

Fig. 1. Geometry of the beam

The assumed displacement field for the beam, based on a higher-order shear deformation theory, is given by the following equation (3), as proposed by Jun & Hongxing [10].

$$\begin{cases} U(x, z) = u(x) + z\varphi(x) + (f(z) - z) \left(\frac{\partial w(x)}{\partial x} + \varphi(x) \right) \\ V(x, z) = f(z)\psi(x) \\ W(x, z) = w(x) \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Where U, V and W are the displacements of an arbitrary point on the beam in the x, y, and z directions, respectively; u and w are the displacements of a point on the mid-plane along the x and z directions, respectively, and φ , ψ are the rotations of the normal to the mid-plane about the x and y axes, respectively. The specified function $f(z)$ will determine the shear stress distribution across the thickness. The Euler-Bernoulli beam theory is a special case based on the kinematic function that vanishes, i.e., $f(z) = 0$.

$f(z)$ satisfies the following conditions:

$$f'(z)|_{z=\pm\frac{h}{2}} = 0 \text{ et } \int_{z=-\frac{h}{2}}^{z=\frac{h}{2}} f(z)dz = 0 \quad (4)$$

The higher-order shear beam model considered in this paper introduces a new shear function $f(z)$ developed by Mechab and Elmeiche and presented below:

$$f(z) = z \cosh\left(\frac{z}{h}\right) - \frac{2(2 \cosh(\frac{1}{2}) + \sinh(\frac{1}{2}))z^2}{\cosh(\frac{1}{2}) + 4 \sinh(\frac{1}{2})} \frac{z^2}{h} \sinh\left(\frac{z}{h}\right) \quad (5)$$

Where (') denotes differentiation with respect to z.

The deformations associated with the displacements in equation (1) are:

$$\begin{cases} \varepsilon_{xx} = \frac{\partial U}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + z \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x} + (f(z) - z) \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x} \right) \\ \gamma_{xy} = \frac{\partial U}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial V}{\partial x} = f(z) \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} = z \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} + (f(z) - z) \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} \\ \gamma_{xz} = \frac{\partial U}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial W}{\partial x} = f'(z) \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} + \varphi \right) \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

3.1. Theory of non-local elasticity, Constitutive relations.

In local elasticity theory, the stress tensor at a material point is assumed to depend on the strain tensor at that point. However, in the theory of non-local elasticity, the stress tensor at one point is assumed to depend on the strain tensor at all points in the continuum. According to Eringen's theory of non-local elasticity [19], the non-local constitutive relations of a Hookean nanomaterial can be represented by the following differential constitutive relation:

$$(1 - \tau^2 \ell^2 \nabla^2) \sigma_{ij}^{NL} = \sigma_{ij}^L = C : \varepsilon, \left(\tau = \frac{e_0 a}{l} \right) \text{ for } i, j = x, y, z \quad (7)$$

The double dot represents the product, ε et C represent the deformation components and elastic constants respectively. $\nabla^2 = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}$ is the Laplacian operator.

The non-local parameter $e_0 a$ parameter has a length dimension and can be greater than 1 In the expression $\tau = \frac{e_0 a}{l} \leq 1$ the value of a depends on the internal length (granular distance, lattice parameter, distance between C-C bonds as molecular diameters, etc.) and l is the external characteristic length (crack length or wavelength). e_0 is a constant specific to each material to adjust the model to obtain reliable results from experiments or other

theories. σ_{ij}^{NL} et σ_{ij}^L respectively represent the tensor components of non-local and local stress in the Cartesian coordinate system. Neglecting the transverse normal stress components, the local constitutive relationships can be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{xx}^L \\ \sigma_{yy}^L \\ \tau_{xy}^L \\ \tau_{yz}^L \\ \tau_{xz}^L \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11}(z) & C_{12}(z) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{12}(z) & C_{22}(z) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C_{66}(z) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44}(z) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{55}(z) \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx}^L \\ \varepsilon_{yy}^L \\ \gamma_{xy}^L \\ \gamma_{yz}^L \\ \gamma_{xz}^L \end{Bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

$$C_{11}(z) = C_{22} = \frac{E(z)}{1-\nu^2}, \quad C_{12} = \frac{\nu E(z)}{1-\nu^2}; \quad C_{44} = C_{55} = C_{66} = G(z) \quad (9)$$

The constitutive equations of an FGM based on the theory of high-order shear deformation can be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_{xx} \\ N_{yy} \\ N_{xy} \\ M_{xx} \\ M_{yy} \\ M_{xy} \\ S_{xx} \\ S_{yy} \\ S_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & 0 & B_{11} & B_{12} & 0 & B_{11}^f & B_{12}^f & 0 \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & 0 & B_{12} & B_{22} & 0 & B_{12}^f & B_{22}^f & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & A_{66} & 0 & 0 & B_{66} & 0 & 0 & B_{66}^f \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & 0 & D_{11} & D_{12} & 0 & D_{11}^f & D_{12}^f & 0 \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & 0 & D_{12} & D_{22} & 0 & D_{12}^f & D_{22}^f & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & B_{66} & 0 & 0 & D_{66} & 0 & 0 & D_{66}^f \\ B_{11}^f & B_{12}^f & 0 & D_{11}^f & D_{12}^f & 0 & F_{11}^f & F_{12}^f & 0 \\ B_{12}^f & B_{22}^f & 0 & D_{12}^f & D_{22}^f & 0 & F_{12}^f & F_{22}^f & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & B_{66}^f & 0 & 0 & D_{66}^f & 0 & 0 & F_{66}^f \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^0 \\ \varepsilon_y^0 \\ \gamma_{xy}^0 \\ k_x^b \\ k_y^b \\ k_{xy}^b \\ k_x^s \\ k_y^s \\ k_{xy}^s \end{Bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} Q_{yz} \\ Q_{xz} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{44}^f & 0 \\ 0 & A_{55}^f \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \gamma_{yz}^s \\ \gamma_{xz}^s \end{Bmatrix}$$

Where N_{xx} , N_{yy} and N_{xy} are forces in the plane, M_{xx} , M_{yy} and M_{xy} ; are the basic components of stress resultants and stress moments, S_{xx} , S_{yy} et S_{xy} are additional stress moments associated with transverse shear effects, and Q_{xz} , Q_{yz} are the transverse shear stress resultants. The laminate stiffness coefficients A_{ij} and $B_{ij} \dots$, are defined in terms of stiffness coefficients $C_{ij}(z)$ as follows:

$$\{A_{ij}, B_{ij}, D_{ij}\} = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \{1, z, z^2\} C_{ij}(z) dz \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 6)$$

$$\{B_{ij}^f, D_{ij}^f, F_{ij}^f\} = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \{f(z) - z, z(f(z) - z), (f(z) - z)^2\} C_{ij}(z) dz \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 6) \quad (11)$$

$$\{A_{ij}^f\} = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \kappa_s \{f'(z)^2\} \bar{C}_{ij} dz \quad (i, j = 4, 5)$$

$$\text{And : } \varepsilon_x^0 = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x}, \quad k_x^b = \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x}, \quad k_{xy}^b = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x}, \quad k_{xy}^s = \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x}, \quad k_x^s = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x}, \quad \gamma_{xz}^s = \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} + \varphi, \quad (12)$$

3.2. Differential equations governing non-local elasticity

The differential equations governing equilibrium can be deduced using the principle of virtual displacement. The principle of virtual work in this case gives:

$$\pi = \frac{b}{2} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \int_S [N_{xx} \varepsilon_x^0 + M_{xx} \kappa_x^b + M_{xy} \kappa_{xy}^b + S_{xx} \kappa_x^s + S_{xy} \kappa_{xy}^s + Q_{xz} \gamma_{xz}^s] dx \quad (1)$$

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L P \left[\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right]^2 dx \quad (2)$$

π is the elastic energy, T is the buckling energy. The equilibrium equations for buckling are deduced using the principle of conservation of energy as applied to a conservative system. The principle can be formulated as follows:

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \delta L dt = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \delta(\pi - T) dt \quad (3)$$

The equilibrium equations can be derived from Equations by integrating the displacement gradients in parts and setting the coefficients δu , $\delta \varphi$, δw and $\delta \psi$ to zero separately,

$$\begin{cases} \delta u: \frac{\partial N_{xx}}{\partial x} = 0 \\ \delta \varphi: \frac{\partial M_{xx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial S_{xx}}{\partial x} - Q_{xz} = 0 \\ \delta w: \frac{\partial^2 S_{xx}}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\partial Q_{xz}}{\partial x} - P w_{,xx} = 0 \\ \delta \psi: \frac{\partial M_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial S_{xy}}{\partial x} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

With boundary conditions:

$$[N_{xx} \delta u_0]_0^L = 0, [(M_{xx} + S_{xx}) \delta \varphi]_0^L = 0; [S_{xx} \delta w_{,x}]_0^L = 0; [(Q_{xz} - S_{xx,x} + P \delta w_{,x}) \delta w]_0^L = 0, [(M_{xy} + S_{xy}) \delta \psi]_0^L = 0 \quad (4)$$

The in-plane force, bending moment and additional stress moments associated with transverse shear effects are then given by:

$$M_x = P \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4} (e_0 a)^4 + D_{11} \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x} + D_{11}^f \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x} \right) + \left(A_{55}^f \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x} \right) - D_{11}^f \frac{\partial^3 \varphi}{\partial x^3} - F_{11}^f \left(\frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4} + \frac{\partial^3 \varphi}{\partial x^3} \right) \right) (e_0 a)^2 \quad (17)$$

$$Q_{xz} - \frac{\partial S_{xx}}{\partial x} = (e_0 a)^2 P \frac{\partial^3 w}{\partial x^3} + A_{55}^f \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} + \varphi \right) - D_{11}^f \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial x^2} - F_{11}^f \left(\frac{\partial^3 w}{\partial x^3} + \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial x^2} \right) \quad (18)$$

$$M_{xy} + S_{xy} = (D_{66} + D_{66}^f) \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} + (D_{66}^f + F_{66}^f) \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} \quad (19)$$

The determinant of the differential equations can be combined into a single differential equation satisfied by U , W , Φ or Ψ , expressed with the deflection variable W

$$a_0 W^{(10)} + a_1 W^{(8)} + a_2 W^{(6)} + a_3 W^{(4)} + a_4 W^{(2)} + a_5 W = 0 \quad (20)$$

In this study, the simple support boundary conditions are examined. These boundary conditions are as follows:

$$U(0) = 0, W(0) = 0, S_{xx}(0) = 0, M_{xx}(0) + S_{xx}(0) = 0, M_{xy}(0) + S_{xy}(0) = 0,$$

$$U(L) = 0, W(L) = 0, S_{xx}(L) = 0, M_{xx}(L) + S_{xx}(L) = 0, M_{xy}(L) + S_{xy}(L) = 0 \quad (21)$$

3.3. Rayleigh-Ritz method

The solution to the above equations can be of the following form:

$$w(x) = B_1 \cos h\left(\frac{\Phi_m x}{L}\right) + B_2 \cos\left(\frac{\Phi_m x}{L}\right) - \mu_m \left(B_3 \sin h\left(\frac{\Phi_m x}{L}\right) + B_4 \sin\left(\frac{\Phi_m x}{L}\right) \right) \quad (22)$$

The axial modal function $\psi(x)$ is chosen as the reference function.

In addition, the axial modal function must satisfy the boundary conditions applied at the ends of the beam, i.e. $x = 0$ and $x = L$, see Table 1.

Table 1. Boundary conditions (S-S).

$B_i(1 - 4)$	Φ_m	μ_m
$B_1 = 0, B_2 = 0, B_3 = 0, B_4 = -1$	$m\pi$	1

4. Numerical results

4.1. Validation of the present model

To demonstrate the validity of our model, a comparative study of non-dimensional critical buckling for an FGM beam without the Poisson's effect or non-local effect is presented. This study introduces a new buckling shape function described in equation (3) and compares the results obtained with different beam buckling theories namely: parabolic shear deformation theory (PSDBT), hyperbolic shear deformation theory e (HSDBT), exponential shear deformation theory (ESDBT) with:

PSDBT: $f(z) = z \left(\frac{1-4z^2}{3h^2} \right)$,

HSDBT: $f(z) = h \sinh(z/h) - z \cosh(1/2)$,

ESDBT: $f(z) = z \exp[-2(z/h)^2]$.

Present: $(z) = f(z) = z \cosh\left(\frac{z}{h}\right) - \frac{2(2 \cosh\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) + \sinh\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)) z^2}{\cosh\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) + 4 \sinh\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} \frac{z^2}{h} \sinh\left(\frac{z}{h}\right)$

FG material properties are assumed to be: $E_t = E_c = 380\text{GPa}$, $E_b = E_m = 70\text{GPa}$ and $\nu_t = \nu_b = 0.3$. The dimensionless critical buckling loads used in this study: $\bar{P}_{cr} = P_{cr} \frac{12L^2}{E_m h^3}$

Table 2. Dimensionless critical buckling load for an articulated-articulated FGM beam with slenderness $L/h = 5$.

	1-0-1	1-1-1	1-2-1	2-1-2	2-1-1	2-2-1
Present	30.7442	34.8112	38.2193	32.8836	34.2424	36.7630
ESDBT	30.7443	34.8113	38.2194	32.8838	34.2425	36.7631
HSDBT	30.7132	34.7934	38.2165	32.8590	34.2235	36.7546
PSDBT	30.7141	34.7936	38.2160	32.8595	34.2238	36.7544
Dif (%)	0.10	0.05	0.01	0.08	0.06	0.02

$$\text{Difference (\%)} = 100 \cdot (\text{Present} - \text{HSDBT}) / \text{HSDBT}$$

The results presented in **Table 2** show an excellent agreement with the established theories of the beams in the different configurations. The percentage differences remain remarkably small, ranging from 0.01% to 0.10%. The largest difference is observed in the 1-0-1 configuration and the smallest in the 1-2-1 case. This consistent performance in the different configurations confirms the robustness and reliability of the current model.

4.2. Poisson's effect on dimensionless critical loads.

In this case we will an analysis of buckling forces with and without the Poisson effect. Table 3 presents the results for beams with slenderness ratios $L/h=5$ and $L/h=20$ and for (1-0-1) FG beam configuration, varying the power index p and non-local coefficient μ . It can be observed that the critical buckling loads are generally lower when Poisson's effect is included, with differences ranging from 8.849% to 32.046% for $L/h=5$ and 6.67% to 30.46% for $L/h=20$. The following general observations can be made: Poisson's ratio tends to reduce critical buckling loads, the impact is more pronounced for larger values of p (more metallic composition), the effect is generally greater for shorter beams ($L/h = 5$) and the combined influence of the Poisson's effect and the non-local effect (μ) amplifies the reduction in critical loads

The relative difference between the cases with and without Poisson's effect varies significantly according to material composition (p) and slenderness ratio. These results highlight the importance of taking Poisson's effect into account when analysing the buckling of composite beams, particularly for short structures and more metallic compositions.

Table 3.a: Poisson's effect on the dimensionless buckling loads for slenderness ratios $L/h=5$.

		L/h=5									
		P=0		P=0.5		P=1		P=5		P=50	
μ		with PE	Without PE								
0		53.291	58.465	29.739	37.440	20.733	28,515	10,622	15,632	9,826	12,819
1		52.008	57.057	29.023	36.539	20.234	27,829	10,367	15,255	9,589	12,511
2		50.785	55.715	28.340	35.680	19.758	27,174	10,123	14,897	9,364	12,216
3		49.618	54.435	27.689	34.860	19.304	26,550	9,890	14,554	9,149	11,936
4		48.504	53.213	27.067	34.077	18.871	25,954	9,668	14,228	8,943	11,668
5		47.439	52.044	26.473	33.329	18.456	25,384	9,456	13,915	8,747	11,411
Diff(%)		8.849		20.570		27.291		32.046		23.349	

$$\text{Diff(\%)} = 100 \times (\text{without PE} - \text{with PE}) / \text{without PE}$$

Table 3.b: Poisson's effect on the dimensionless buckling loads for slenderness ratios $L/h=20$.

		L/h=20									
		P=0		P=0.5		P=1		P=5		P=50	
μ		with PE	Without PE								
0		49.336	52.916	27.857	34.793	19.652	26.836	10.146	15.021	9.071	12.366
1		35.372	37.938	19.973	24.945	14.090	19.240	7.274	10.769	6.504	8.866
2		27.569	29.569	15.567	19.442	10.982	14.996	5.670	8.394	5.069	6.910

3	22.586	24.225	12.753	15.928	8.997	12.285	4.645	6.877	4.153	5.661
4	19.129	20.517	10.801	13.490	7.620	10.405	3.934	5.824	3.517	4.795
5	16.590	17.793	9.367	11.700	6.608	9.024	3.412	5.051	3.050	4.158
Diff(%)	6.77		19.94		26.77		30.46		26.64	

4.3. Parametric study with non-local effect and p power law, considering Poisson's effect

The beam presented in Figure 1 is the subject of consideration. The results displayed in Table 4 illustrate the variation of dimensionless buckling loads as a function of the nonlocal parameter μ and the power law index p for different layer configurations and slenderness ratios, with the consideration of Poisson's effect.

The variation of the dimensionless critical load as a function of μ and p for the different beam layer configurations for slenderness ratios $L/h=2.5$, $L/h=5$ and $L/h=20 = 20$ is given in Tables 4.a, 4.b, and 4.c. It can be observed that for $L/h = 2.5$ (Table 4.a), for $p = 0$, the critical load is identical for all configurations. This indicates that the beam is homogeneous (ceramic). As μ increases, there is a progressive decrease in the critical load, which is 61.23% between $\mu = 0$ and $\mu = 1$, 37.98% between $\mu = 1$ and $\mu = 2$, and 17.75% for $\mu = 4$ to $\mu = 5$. Due to the predominance of the metallic material, the values of the dimensionless critical load decrease significantly for $\mu = 50$ and above. The effect of the parameter p has a significant influence, since there is a significant reduction in the critical load values, with $\bar{P}_{cr}=39.89$ for $p=0$ and $\bar{P}_{cr}=7.6219$ for $p=50$.

Table 4.a: Variation of dimensionless buckling loads as a function of μ and p parameters for different layer configurations for slenderness ratios $L/h=2.5$.

μ	p	1-0-1	1-1-1	1-2-1	2-1-2	2-1-1	2-2-1
0	0	39.8987	39.8987	39.8987	39.8987	39.8987	39.8987
	0.5	24.0825	27.4294	29.6849	25.9309	26.7156	28.4779
	1	17.4036	21.6375	24.7774	19.6646	20.7001	23.0679
	5	9.1309	12.5959	16.3631	10.7317	11.8733	14.3024
	50	7.6219	10.4486	13.7836	9.0962	10.1310	12.0362
1	0	15.4698	15.4698	15.4698	15.4698	15.4698	15.4698
	0.5	9.3374	10.6351	11.5096	10.0541	10.3584	11.0416
	1	6.7478	8.3894	9.6069	7.6245	8.0260	8.9440
	5	3.5403	4.8838	6.3444	4.1610	4.6036	5.5454
	50	2.9552	4.0512	5.3443	3.5268	3.9281	4.6667
3	0	6.9541	6.9541	6.9541	6.9541	6.9541	6.9541
	0.5	4.1975	4.7808	5.1739	4.5196	4.6564	4.9635
	1	3.0334	3.7713	4.3186	3.4274	3.6079	4.0206
	5	1.5915	2.1954	2.8520	1.8705	2.0695	2.4928
	50	1.3284	1.8211	2.4024	1.5854	1.7658	2.0978
4	0	5.4532	5.4532	5.4532	5.4532	5.4532	5.4532
	0.5	3.2915	3.7489	4.0572	3.5441	3.6514	3.8923
	1	2.3787	2.9573	3.3865	2.6877	2.8292	3.1528
	5	1.2480	1.7216	2.2364	1.4668	1.6228	1.9548
	50	1.0417	1.4281	1.8839	1.2432	1.3847	1.6451

	0	4.4852	4.4852	4.4852	4.4852	4.4852	4.4852
	0.5	2.7072	3.0834	3.3370	2.9150	3.0032	3.2013
5	1	1.9564	2.4324	2.7853	2.2106	2.3270	2.5932
	5	1.0264	1.4160	1.8394	1.2064	1.3347	1.6078
	50	0.8568	1.1746	1.5495	1.0225	1.1389	1.3530

b. For $L/h = 20$ (Table 4.b):

- For $p = 0$ the critical load is identical for all configurations.
- As μ increases, the critical load decreases much more slowly than for short beams, where it is of the order of 2% for different μ intervals.
- The effect of the parameter p has a significant influence with the same rates of decrease of the values of the dimensionless critical load.

Table 4.b: Variation of dimensionless buckling loads as a function of μ and p parameters for different layer configurations for slenderness ratios $L/h=20$.

μ	p	1-0-1	1-1-1	1-2-1	2-1-2	2-1-1	2-2-1
0	0	53.2912	53.2912	53.2912	53.2912	53.2912	53.2912
	0.5	29.7389	34.1117	37.3454	32.0768	33.2625	35.6680
	1	20.7334	25.9748	30.2512	23.4349	24.8947	27.9719
	5	10.6224	14.2341	18.8963	12.0930	13.5576	16.3902
	50	13.6348	11.6723	15.6337	10.2936	11.6193	13.6348
1	0	52.0080	52.0080	52.0080	52.0080	52.0080	52.0080
	0.5	29.0228	33.2903	36.4462	31.3044	32.4615	34.8091
	1	20.2341	25.3493	29.5227	22.8706	24.2953	27.2984
	5	10.3666	13.8913	18.4413	11.8018	13.2312	15.9955
	50	13.3064	11.3912	15.2572	10.0457	11.3408	13.3064
3	0	49.6184	49.6184	49.6184	49.6184	49.6184	49.6184
	0.5	27.6893	31.7607	34.7716	29.8661	30.9700	33.2097
	1	19.3044	24.1846	28.1662	21.8197	23.1790	26.0441
	5	9.8903	13.2530	17.5940	11.2596	12.6232	15.2605
	50	12.6951	10.8678	14.5562	9.5841	10.8220	12.6951
4	0	48.5041	48.5041	48.5041	48.5041	48.5041	48.5041
	0.5	27.0675	31.0474	33.9907	29.1954	30.2745	32.4639
	1	18.8709	23.6414	27.5337	21.3297	22.6584	25.4592
	5	9.6682	12.9554	17.1989	11.0067	12.3398	14.9178
	50	12.4100	10.6238	14.2293	9.3689	10.5800	12.4100
5	0	47.4387	47.4387	47.4387	47.4387	47.4387	47.4387
	0.5	26.4730	30.3655	33.2441	28.5541	29.6095	31.7509
	1	18.4564	23.1222	26.9289	20.8612	22.1607	24.9000
	5	9.4559	12.6709	16.8211	10.7649	12.0687	14.5902
	50	12.1374	10.3904	13.9168	9.1631	10.3486	12.1374

Figs. 2-3 show the evolution of the critical load as a function of μ for different values of p and L/h ratio, as well as for different configurations of the sandwich beam. Figure 2 shows a non-linear variation of the critical load, with a significant decrease in the values between $\mu = 0$ and $\mu = 1$. This variation tends to stabilise for higher values of μ . The curves overlap for $p = 0$ due to the homogeneous composition of the beam (ceramic). The curves separate

as p increases and we see that the (1-2-1) configuration always gives the highest value. Note also that the curves become increasingly linear from $L/h = 10$ and are linear for $L/h = 20$. For long beams, the variation tends towards a horizontal limit, which means that the effect of μ is less significant. The drop in \bar{P}_{Cr} values is very marked for short beams ($L/h=2.5$), where P_{cr} drops from 40 to 5 for $p=0$, whereas for slender beams ($L/h=20$) the difference is much smaller (\bar{P}_{Cr} drops from 53 to 47.5). This difference in behaviour is due to the shear effect, which is very important for short beams, whereas for other beams the bending effect predominates.

Fig. 2.: Dimensionless Critical Buckling Loads as a Function of μ , for various ply configurations and power law index p . $L/h = 2.5$

Fig. 3.: Dimensionless Critical Buckling Loads as a Function of μ , for various ply configurations and power law index p . $L/h = 20$

5. Conclusion

This study investigates the buckling analysis of functionally graded (FG) sandwich beams using Eringen's non-local theory. A high-order displacement field model is employed, incorporating transverse shear along the beam width and considering Poisson's effect. A novel warping shape function is introduced to enhance the accuracy of the analysis. The equilibrium equations, derived analytically using the energy principle, are solved numerically using the Ritz method based on energy minimization. The model was validated,

and the results demonstrate good agreement with high-order beam theory models, showing negligible differences. The study leads to the following conclusions:

- The non-local effect (μ) is more pronounced for short beams, which is crucial for the design of nano-beams.
- The results indicate that the buckling behaviour of beams is significantly influenced by the interaction between the geometrical parameters (L/h), the power parameter (p), and the non-local effect (μ).
- The study reveals that Poisson's effect is significant in all the examples examined.

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